

Acute central nervous system disorders in medical emergency

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Abstract

Acute central nervous system disorders are a direct threat to life and should therefore be recognized and treated as soon as possible. Brain damage is one of the most common causes of death. Detailed below are detailed symptomatic disease units designed to facilitate rapid diagnosis of the disorder and to decide whether to transport the patient to the appropriate medical center as soon as possible. Diagnostic options for diagnosing a disease such as a cerebral ischemic stroke or subarachnoid hematoma have been significantly developed over the years. Studies such as computer tomography or magnetic resonance imaging are extremely important for making a quick diagnosis. The development of technology and knowledge of the central nervous system has significantly reduced the number of deaths caused by cerebral disorders. The most important link in the procedure is a quick and accurate diagnosis of life threatening symptoms.

Keywords: Central Nervous System, stroke, neurology, medical emergency

Anatomy of the Central Nervous System - basic organization of the nervous system

The nervous system participates in the process of informing the body about what is happening in itself and in the surrounding world. It is composed of strictly integrated units. The nervous system processes information to accommodate changes in the external and internal environment and then sends instructions to different organs. The central nervous system consists of the brain and spinal cord, enclosed within the skull, and the spine, the skeletal structure that protects vital organs. The main areas of the brain are cerebral cortex, subcortical structures, cerebral cortex and cerebellum [1]. The cerebral hemispheres separate the midrange from the middle and are connected to the corpus callosum through which the nerve pathways pass, allowing communication between the hemispheres. The right and left cortex is divided into four lobes. The most frontal is the frontal lobe. Although anatomically both frontal lobes look similar, they definitely differ in function. The dominating nature of the left hemisphere results in almost all right-handed people, and in at least half of left-handed people, areas associated with speech initiation within the left frontal lobe. In the appropriate areas of the frontal lobe of the frontal cortex, any motor activity begins [1, 2]. Higher functions such as problem solving ability, reasoning and a large part of our personality are located

in the frontal lobes. Spontaneity of thinking and ingenuity, even if they are not assigned to one area, are most disturbed in the event of damage to these areas. Directly back from the frontal lobes lie the parietal lobes. They are the main area for receiving sensory information and information from other parts of the body.

These patches are particularly involved in recognizing one's own personality, especially in the imagination and consciousness of the position of the body. Their function is also spatial orientation and three-dimensional perception of objects. The occipital lobes are most rearward. They end up with visual pathways and it makes them realize what we see. Below the frontal and parietal lobes are the temporal lobes separated from them by the lateral line (Sylvia). They are involved in the reception and monitoring of hearing [2, 3].

Autonomic nervous system

The autonomic nervous system is divided into a sympathetic and parasympathetic system. The sympathetic system is the body's alert system. Its stimulation causes: tachycardia, bronchial enlargement, adrenaline release, intestinal peristalsis release, bladder function inhibition, and dilated pupils and dilated pupils. Stimulation of the parasympathetic system results in the opposite effects: bradycardia, bronchoconstriction, excessive salivation and tearing, dilated pupils, as well as

1 Phot. Brain anatomy & functions

Origins: <http://anatomytime.com/body/human-brain-anatomy.html>

acceleration of intestinal peristalsis. Both sympathetic and parasympathetic systems have a very wide impact and often overlap with the functioning of other body systems. Therefore, this part of the nervous system is not routinely evaluated in emergency departments, except in the assessment of basic vital functions [4, 5].

Headache – interview

Headaches may be disorders of the central nervous system of different origins. It is therefore important to conduct a detailed interview with questions about:

- duration of illness;
- Frequency of occurrence and duration of headache;
- time of attack;
- initial symptoms;
- Places and radiation of pain;
- Quality assessment of pain;
- accompanying symptoms;
- triggers;
- Factors that aggravate headache;
- Factors that bring relief;
- Previous treatment.

Due to the duration of the illness, the possible cases can be divided into three main groups: acute, subacute and chronic. This simple division helps reduce the number of diagnostic options that need to be taken into account.

It is important to have head and neck injuries in the past. Subhepatic hematoma can be preceded by a head

traumatized by the patient. Occurrence of numerous episodes known as "encephalitis" or the appearance of headaches associated with neck stiffness should raise suspicion of bleeding from various forms of cerebral vascular defect. A useful symptom in the diagnosis of subarachnoid haemorrhage is the occurrence of root pains in the back, buttocks and thighs, occurring a few hours or days after the onset of headache. They are caused by the blood flowing down through the subarachnoid space towards the tail. First and foremost, however, be aware of the elapsed time. If a paramedic or physician notices a life-threatening symptom, he or she must immediately decide on the required treatment and depart from a detailed headache interview [6, 7].

Disturbances of consciousness

Consciousness depends on the integrated functions of a large part of the brain, including the brainstem, and any abnormalities are a sensitive indicator of central nervous system abnormalities. For this reason, even harmless states like the effects of narcotic drugs or narcotic confusion can result in disturbances of consciousness. At the same time, they may be the first signs of a developing pathology in the brain, and early diagnosis and appropriate treatment will avoid permanent damage. The task of paramedic is therefore to quickly identify and assess the status of cognitive disorders and to distinguish between harmless and serious conditions [8, 9].

Causes of coma and disturbances of consciousness:

- injury;

- infections;
- stroke;
- seizures;
- hypertensive encephalopathy;
- hypoxia;
- ischemia;
- Hypoglycemia;
- hyperglycemia;
- electrolyte disorders;
- hepatic and renal insufficiency;
- Alcohol poisoning;
- Medicines.

In a patient with severe impairment of consciousness or coma:

- Evaluate and stabilize vital activities.
- Determine whether the disorder leading to such a condition is structural or generalized.
- Implement procedures to maintain vital functions.
- Determine a relatively accurate diagnosis [9,10].

Transient Ischemic Attack

Transient ischemic attack (TIA) is defined as the occurrence of neurological symptoms of ischemic etiology, lasting less than 24 hours. Most attacks last from a few minutes to an hour. There is more than one mechanism leading to an ischemic attack. The TIA mechanism may consist of transient arterial thrombosis resulting from critical stenosis within the carotid artery or vertebral artery. In such cases the symptoms persist for a short time. Attacks in patients without critical arterial stenosis last longer and are usually associated with arterial occlusive arterial occlusion, indicating the potential arterial thromboembolism resulting from the formation of emboli within the ulcer at the surface of the atherosclerotic plaque or from another proximal embolic source. In some cases, TIA can develop in the course of hemodynamic disturbances, including transient hypotension and arrhythmias. If symptoms disappear after administration of calcium channel blockers, vasoconstriction is the primary cause of the incidence.

2. Phot. Autonomic nervous system

Figure 45-20 Biological Science, 2/e
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3. Phot. Brain vascularisation - brain artery (Willis)

The cause of the attack may also be primary cerebrovascular disease [11, 12].

Ischemic stroke

Symptoms of ischemia in particular areas of vascularisation are not dependent only on the location of vascular occlusion, but also on pre-existing brain damage, peripheral circulation capacity, and vascularization area of a given cerebral artery. For example, occlusion of the internal carotid artery can cause the lower limbs of the lower limbs. Occurrence of symptoms typical for a particular cerebrospinal fluid does not always help to determine the location and cause of obstruction. For example, ischemia in the area of central cerebral artery vascularisation is often the result of an internal carotid artery thrombosis. Nevertheless, knowledge of

symptomatic syndromes associated with vascular territories helps in locating the lesion and whether it is vascular or not [2, 5].

Ectopic hematoma

Brain edema and hematoma are the main causes of intracranial tightness. Ectopic hematoma is an accumulation of blood in the epidural space between the outer surface of the hard tire and the skull bone. Most often, these hematomas are caused by damage to the trunk or branches of the medial carotid artery, which is easily damaged by bone fracture. Sometimes the artery is damaged only due to the elastic defecation of the bone due to the injury. As a rule, hematoma is formed at the site of an artery injury. Placement of epidural hematoma in the temporal and parietal and temporal regions occurs in

about 80% of cases and the remaining 20% is "atypical" [5].

Subhepatic hematoma

Subterranean hemorrhage, the most common complication of cranio-cerebral traumas, produces blood in the space between the arachnoid of the cerebral hemisphere and the inner surface of the sclera. Subspace space is a potential gap in which collecting blood is spilled freely, most often over the frontal-parietal region, but often over the entire hemisphere. The origin of subdural hematoma is hemorrhage from damaged veins draining blood from the surface of the brain that goes mainly to the upper sagittal sinus, but also to other sinuses. Movement of the brain at the moment of injury in the mechanism of acceleration / delay leads to tension and the strangling of these veins, and bloody spilling in the subdural space. More often, subdural hematoma - its "acute" form (the most common) - is caused by mixed arteriovenous haemorrhage in the cervical fissures and brain rupture. Subdural haematomas were divided into three clinical forms: acute, subacute and chronic. The recurring criterion is the time when the hematoma appears. This breakdown is justified by the course, treatment outcome and prognosis. Symptoms that dominate the whole of the clinical picture are almost always independent of the presence of this head trauma. Hemiparesis is only an "add-on" to major damage, which is severe, usually multifocal bruising or rupture of the brain, with spreading outbreaks of edema leading to intracranial movements and cerebral cortex [5, 11].

Intracerebral haemorrhage

Intracerebral haemorrhage is the accumulation of blood in the cerebral parenchyma. Most of these hematomas occur in the most common contusions in the frontal and temporal areas. Initially, these may be minor breakdowns with the accompanying thrombosis. Hypoxia and acidification of the tissue increases capillary permeability, causing further damage to brain tissue and further haemorrhages that combine to form the "bloody surrender" of the brain surface. With the increase in volume, they dig deep into the brain and become the substance of the intracerebral hematoma.

If complete bleeding stops, hematoma in the intracerebral haemorrhage can further increase volume, destroying subcortical brain structures. Patients with single or even large hemispheres of the brain that do not trigger intracranial and cerebral infarction symptoms can be treated conservatively with osmotic and diuretic agents, with blood osmolarity monitoring, under strict clinical management, especially with observation of the state of consciousness and control neurological [3, 13, 14].

Concussion

A cerebral shock syndrome is a series of clinical symptoms in which unconsciousness as a sudden sequelae of sudden head trauma is a guiding symptom. "Shock is thought to be immediate post-traumatic brain dysfunction combined with unconsciousness (Gurdjian). According to the theory of the emergence of this state, there are two groups of views:

1. shock associated with immediate loss of consciousness is due to damage to the brainstem structures, and reversibility or irreversibility of this condition is dependent on the severity of the injury;
2. unconsciousness, which is the main symptom of shock, is the result of damage to the cerebral cortex."

Post-traumatic loss of consciousness is a complex phenomenon, and consists of temporal generalization of neural activity associated with cerebral cortex and deep structures involving the brainstem. The duration of unconsciousness can last from a few seconds to a dozen or so minutes, several hours and even days. The cause of prolonged unconsciousness may be morphological brain damage in the form of edema accompanying contusions of fracture or other causes including extracorporeal. Stroke of the brain is usually accompanied by retrograde amnesia. The moment in which the sick person has an accident is extinguished from his memory [5,6].

Cerebral edema

Brain edema is a state of increased brain tissue volume resulting from the accumulation of water and from elevated sodium levels in the tissues. In the case of localization in clinically silent or mild cases, it can lead only to mild impairment of brain function or even dementia clinically. In severe cases, both focal and generalized symptoms are observed, primarily in the form of brain entrapment and damage to the circulatory and respiratory centers located in the extended core. The hooking may also involve the hook of the hippocampus, the tonsils of the cerebellum, the upper part of the cerebellum (above the indentation of the tent), the rim of the rim (under the brain) and other structures of the brain (under the tent, into the surrounding vessel).

There are three types of edema:

1. Vascular (vasculine),
2. Cellular (cytotoxic),
3. Interstitial (associated with hydrocephalus [1, 6].

Epilepsy

"Epileptic seizures are one of the subgroups of seizures of cerebral origin. Therefore, the statement that

someone with a cerebral-origin attack does not mean a mechanism of epilepsy.

Epileptic seizure is a manifestation of violent and excessive discharge of nerve cells by depolarization of the cell membrane. This disorder is accompanied by bioelectrical discharges of neurons and clinical signs of motor, sensory, emotional, vegetative, cognitive or emotional disturbances; At the same time, there are often combinations of these disorders. If seizures are repeated, we talk about epilepsy; One attack is epilepsy; Seizures must repeat. How many times must the attack be repeated - it is a contractual matter. We generally assume that two seizures or more, occurring without a sensible cause, such as fever, alcohol, poisoning, etc., give rise to the diagnosis of epilepsy. But epilepsy can be diagnosed after the first attack, if EEG has a pathological record. Epileptic seizures can be a normal response of nerve cells to an abnormal stimulus. In contrast, in epilepsy, a seizure may result from an abnormal response of nerve cells even to a normal stimulus. Interpersonal differences in responses are due not only to the strength and type of stimulus, but also to the innate epilepsy threshold and brain condition (epileptic seizure) at the time of epileptic activity [1,5, 8, 15].

Emergency medicine

The role of a paramedic is a very important diagnostic element. From the time of arrival of the medical rescue team to the patient should take as little time as possible to properly diagnose, transport to the hospital and implement appropriate treatment. Two scales are used to quickly assess a patient's neurological status:

1. **AVPU Scale** - used to assess consciousness:

- A (Alert) - conscious
- V (Verbal) - responds to voice commands
- P (Pain) - responds to pain stimulus
- U (Unresponsive) - unconscious, does not respond to any stimuli

2. **Glasgow Scale (Glasgow Coma Scale - GCS)** - used for assessment of consciousness.

The assessment is subject to:

1. Open your eyes

- Spontaneous - 4 points
- On command - 3 points
- For pain stimuli - 2 points
- Does not open eyes - 1 point

2. Verbal contact

- Logical, oriented - 5 points
- Tangled - 4 points
- Inappropriate words - 3 points
- Unintelligible sounds, groans - 2 points
- No reaction - 1 point

3. Motion reaction

- Conforms to the command - 6 points

- Locates the stimulus - 5 points
- The withdrawal reaction in response to pain - 4 points
- Pathologic flexural response (rooting) - 3 points
- Pathological Straight Response (reflex) - 2 points
- No response - 1 point

Based on this scale, the disturbance of consciousness is divided into:

- GCS 13-15 - mild
- GCS 9-12 - moderate
- GCS 6-8 - unconsciousness
- GCS 5 - rendition
- GCS 4 - rejuvenation
- GCS 3 - cerebral death

Assessing the patient with these scales should take as short a time as possible. Another important element is the gathering of interviews from the patient and / or his family. In the case of ischemic stroke the most valuable information is the time of symptoms such as aphasia. If it is a fresh stroke that will be properly diagnosed and the patient is quickly transported to the hospital, it is possible to implement thrombolytic treatment that reduces the risk of neurological deficiency. SAMPLE has been developed to improve the intelligence gathering technique.

- S (Symptoms / Signs) - signs / symptoms
- A (Allergies) - allergies
- M (Medicines) - medications
- P (Past medical history) - past diseases
- L (Last oral intake) - the last meal
- E (Event leading to injury / illness) - possibly resulting in injury or illness?

If the patient is an accident victim and the rescuer decides to treat the patient as traumatic, the basic vital functions of the ABCDE scheme should be assessed:

- A - Airways - breathing airways
 - B - Breath Assessment
 - C - Circulation - Circulation assessment
 - D - Drugs / Disability / Defibrillation - drugs, injuries, possible defibrillation
 - E - Expose and Examine - Reveal and explore
- Sometimes there is the ABCDEFG combo, where
- F - Fluids - is the implementation of fluid therapy
 - G - Go quickly! / Glucose - a reminder for the rescuer to act quickly, as the injured patient should be in the hospital within the so-called. Golden hour; Reminds about the glucose test

After evaluating the ABC and failing to stop breathing or circulating, one of the paramedics performs a complete traumatic head-to-toe test. When examining the head, it is important to keep a close eye on the ear, as there may be spinal fluid leakage or a fracture of the base of the skull.

Such a fracture can also be witnessed by the appearance of the "eye of a shed", otherwise referred to as ocular hematoma. It is also important to evaluate the pupils. Their width, symmetry and reaction to light. By going further in the neck, it is important to remember to wear an orthopedic collar to avoid secondary damage to the cervical spine, including the spinal cord. After examining the entire body and providing any injuries or injuries, place the injured person on an orthopedic board and transport him or her to the ambulance. Where should a re-examination with body exposure. The rescuer also tests parameters such as:

- Frequency of breathing
- Saturation
- HR - heart rate
- RR - blood pressure
- Blood glucose concentration

If the patient is conscious the paramedic should check if the patient has not had muscle weakness, paresis or paralysis of the limbs. This can be checked by grasping the hands of the victim with his hands and asking them to tighten them as hard as possible. Anxiety disorders can be a result of taking drugs or stimulants. If it is possible to identify a substance that has been taken by the patient, such as a medicine or vomit pack, the paramedics job is to protect the substance or package and give it to the doctor after reaching the hospital.

However, if the paramedic is confident that the patient has become poisoned with benzodiazepine drugs or opioids, he or she can give Flumazenil or Naloxon, respectively. If a medical rescuer suspects a stroke in a patient, he or she should give him a 30 ° elevation position to facilitate the flow of venous blood to the heart. In pre-hospital care it is not possible to assess whether ischemic or haemorrhagic stroke has occurred because the symptoms are the same in both cases. So the process is the same. The patient must be transported to the hospital as soon as possible to control the vital parameters. If the saturation (SpO₂) is below normal (> 95%), paramedics should use passive oxygen therapy, providing high oxygen flow through the face mask with the reservoir connected. High blood pressure values are not indications for the administration of hypotensive drugs. The only indication to lower the pressure when a stroke is suspected is a hypertensive crisis (hypertension) when the blood pressure is above 220/120 mmHg. Paramedics also have the task of providing mental and thermal comfort to the patient. This patient must be rushed to the hospital as soon as possible in order to allow the doctor to further diagnose [5].

The management of epileptic seizures in pre-hospital conditions is primarily to provide airway obstruction,

oxygen therapy, intravenous injection and injury prevention. Do not put anything in your mouth, as they may provoke vomiting or a tooth fracture. Patients with convulsions may require urgent glycemia, and if this is not possible, empirical glucose is permitted. If the attack lasts longer than a minute ball is administered intravenously 5 mg diazepam every minute to a total dose of 20 mg, Lorazepam can also be used in intravenous 2 mg every minute to a maximum dose of 10 mg. Intramuscular administration of midazolam or rectal administration of diazepam is used when intravenous injection can not be assumed. Patients with a first-life epileptic seizure should be transported to rescue units, if possible by specialist ambulance. Patients with a recognized epilepsy who have had a typical attack and have no symptoms in a neurological examination do not require transportation to the hospital if they are familiar with the disease and know the indications for treatment. However, they should be advised as soon as possible to contact a primary care physician. The remaining patients should be transported to the emergency department [2, 5, 12].

Consider the potential for treatment for the condition of epilepsy. Otherwise, controlling seizures will be difficult. You need to provide comprehensive care, including oxygen therapy, intravenous contact, diagnosis and initiation of pharmacological treatment. Oxygen therapy is monitored by pulse oximetry. In case of respiratory failure, intubation is recommended. Long-acting relaxants may only be switched on after electroencephalographic monitoring is provided, as they may hamper the clinical judgment that pharmacotherapy depends on. Urgently need to determine the blood glucose level and if glucose is lower than 80mg / dl glucose is recommended. If this determination is not possible, 50 ml of 50% intravenous glucose in adults and 2 ml / kg of 25% glucose in children are administered. Thiamine 100 mg is recommended with glucose bolus in patients who are alcoholic or underarmed. If an infection is suspected, the antibiotic is switched on because the CT scan of the head or lumbar puncture may be delayed until the patient is stabilized. In patients suspected of drug overdose use activated carbon at a dose of 1g / kg body weight [5, 14].

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is important to note the role of medical rescuer in acute CNS disorders. It is the second link in the rescue chain, taking into account the call for help by the witness of the incident. In emergency medicine you may encounter a number of symptoms that may indicate a neurological disorder. To properly diagnose the patient, you should know the basic information about the disorder and perform a basic

neurological examination with an interview that is the key to diagnosis for any medical practitioner.

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Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.